

Discovery of antileishmanial compounds from *Artemisia umbelliformis* subsp. *eriantha* using HeteroCovariance Approach, HetCA

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ABSTRACT

Natural product drug discovery faces important challenges related to efficient complex mixture analysis. To address this, dereplication strategies have been developed to enhance and accelerate the detection of bioactive compounds in plant extracts. Among these, statistical spectroscopy-based methods HeteroCovariance Approach (HetCA) and Statistical Total Correlation Spectroscopy (STOCSY) have been proposed. In this study, HetCA and STOCSY are applied to *Artemisia umbelliformis* subsp. *eriantha* extract, to discover antileishmanial compounds. Spectral data from appropriately generated extract fractions were statistically correlated with antileishmanial activity results. HetCA along with STOCSY revealed sets of NMR signals correlated to the activity and led to the identification of specific bioactive compounds. These components were purposefully isolated and tested against *L. infantum* promastigotes, designating that the positively correlated compounds 5-deoxy-5-hydroperoxytelekin 1 and telekin 2 exert strong antileishmanial effects, with a half-maximal effective concentration (EC₅₀) of 4.5 and 5.1 μM, respectively. Their toxicity was also tested on model host cells, THP-1 macrophages, yielding a 50 % cytotoxic concentration of 29.7 μM and 15 μM, respectively. For verification purposes, non-correlated compounds were also isolated and didn't show significant antileishmanial activity. Overall, the combination of HetCA and STOCSY was able to identify the most active compounds, facilitating the detection of bioactive components and opening new insights into natural product drug discovery.

1. Introduction

Natural products remain a vital source of novel therapeutic compounds for drug discovery [1]. However, identifying bioactive compounds from complex mixtures, such as plant extracts, presents significant challenges. The traditional bioactivity-guided isolation approach involves iterative cycles of chromatographic separation and bioactivity assessment, making it a time-consuming and labor-intensive process. This approach often leads to the repeated isolation and identification of known compounds, further complicating the discovery of new bioactive molecules. To address these challenges, dereplication

methods have been developed to streamline isolation processes and enhance the detection of minor bioactive compounds [2]. Metabolomics has emerged as a powerful tool in natural products research, integrating spectroscopic techniques with multivariate statistical analyses to expedite the characterization of complex plant extracts [3]. The two most used analytical techniques in metabolomics are mass spectrometry (MS) and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy. NMR, in particular, is advantageous due to its rapid, highly reproducible, cost effective, and non-destructive nature. Within NMR-based metabolomics, Statistical Spectroscopy tools have been developed namely Statistical Total Correlation Spectroscopy (STOCSY) [4] and Statistical

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Heterospectroscopy (SHY) [5,6] assisting the correct assignment of the different metabolites. STOCSY facilitates the correlation of NMR signals originating from the same molecule by leveraging intensity-based multicollinearity across multiple spectra. Initially applied to biological samples [7], STOCSY has found promising applications in the analysis of natural products and food matrices [8–10], however still highly underutilized. On the other hand, SHY data could verify metabolite annotation by correlating MS and NMR data. Extending further this approach, we developed a statistical tool focusing on natural complex mixtures such as extracts namely HeteroCovariance Approach (HetCA) to facilitate the detection of bioactives [11]. HetCA correlates spectral data from extracts with bioactivity results, enabling the identification of NMR signals associated with biological activity against specific targets. The aim is to streamline the process by leveraging the natural fluctuations in compound concentrations and correlating these variations with respective fluctuations in bioactivity. This concentration gradient exists in closely related natural extracts, such as those from different species, plant parts, or growth conditions, necessitating a high number of samples. Alternatively, an artificial concentration gradient can be created through fractionation using chromatography-based separation techniques. This separation process forces compounds into distinct fractions with altered concentrations, which can then be analyzed and correlated with bioactivity outcomes for each fraction. In principle, any chromatographic separation technique could be explored for this approach, provided that it creates fluctuation in components' concentrations. In this study, Centrifugal Partition Chromatography (CPC) was selected as separation method since it demonstrates important advantages compared to traditional techniques such as high repeatability, large loading capacity, and absence of a solid stationary phase which allows a complete recovery of the sample [12]. Moreover, its scalability its excellent allowing high fractions yield for further elaboration while being a “green” technique since water is commonly used in high percentage. This workflow was first applied to *Paeonia mascula* [13] and *Morus alba* extracts [14] demonstrating its potential for rapidly identifying bioactive natural products before engaging in labor-intensive purification and structural elucidation processes.

Leishmaniasis constitutes an umbrella term for a group of important vector borne diseases caused by protozoan parasites of the genus *Leishmania*, which are transmitted by the bite of female phlebotomine sandflies [15]. *Leishmania* parasites share a digenetic life cycle and live either as extracellular, motile promastigotes within the midgut of their sand fly vector, or as intracellular, non-motile amastigotes in professional phagocytes of the mammalian host [15]. Leishmaniasis is endemic in approximately 100 countries and presents a broad spectrum of clinical outcomes ranging from self-healing localized skin lesions (Cutaneous Leishmaniasis, CL) to lethal, if left untreated, systemic disease (Visceral Leishmaniasis, VL) [16]. Control of leishmaniasis, depends solely on drugs, since human vaccines are unavailable. There is a multitude of limitations from current chemotherapy, including their limited armory, high toxicity and loss of efficacy due to development of drug resistance [17]. Leishmaniasis remains a major global health concern, with an estimated 12 million people currently infected and approximately one billion at risk [18]. In particular, the disease is increasingly widespread, endemic, or emerging in the European Union and its neighboring regions [19]. Despite this, leishmaniasis is often neglected and underreported [20], further highlighting the urgent need for the discovery of new drugs to combat this growing health threat. In

this study, HetCA and STOCSY were applied to an extract of *Artemisia umbelliformis* subsp. *eriantha* to identify compounds with potential antileishmanial activity. The selection of this specific extract was based on pre-existing data obtained from the *in vitro* evaluation of potential anti-leishmanial properties of various Greek *Artemisia* species, where *Artemisia umbelliformis* subsp. *eriantha* ethyl acetate extract exhibited interesting activity against *Leishmania infantum* promastigotes. *Artemisia* species have been traditionally used in medicine for centuries, particularly for treating viral, bacterial, parasitic, and autoimmune diseases [21,22]. Scientific interest in this genus has surged in recent years following the discovery of artemisinin, a sesquiterpene lactone from *Artemisia annua* that serves as a first-line treatment for malaria caused by *Plasmodium falciparum* [23]. Artemisinin-based therapies have saved millions of lives, particularly in regions such as Southeast Asia, Africa, and South America [24]. Given the success of artemisinin, other *Artemisia* species have been investigated for their antiparasitic properties, including their potential efficacy against leishmaniasis [25,26]. Specifically for *Artemisia umbelliformis* subsp. *eriantha* (syn. *Artemisia petrosa* BAUMG.), the species under investigation belongs to the *génépi* group of *Artemisia* species, which are aromatic plants traditionally used to produce the well-known *génépi* liqueur, popular in Alpine regions. These species are endemic to the Alps and Pyrenees but also occur in the mountainous regions of the western and central Mediterranean [27]. In Greece, *A. umbelliformis* subsp. *eriantha* is located at high altitudes in North-Central Greece, including North Pindos, Grammos, Olympus, Smolikias, and Tymphe [28]. To date, only a few phytochemical studies have been reported concerning this subspecies [27] mostly focusing on its essential oil composition [29,30]. Overall, this study represents the first comprehensive evaluation of the antileishmanial activity of *A. umbelliformis* subsp. *eriantha*, contributing valuable insights into its prospective as a source of novel bioactive compounds. It also marks the first application of HetCA in analyzing bioactivity data concerning whole organisms such as *Leishmania* parasites, as the approach has been sporadically used for the identification of actives against specific pharmacological targets, mainly enzymes. Validation of the process by further isolation of the compounds demonstrated the potential of HetCA in rationalization of natural product discovery.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. General experimental procedures

For CPC a FCPC1000® apparatus (Kromaton, Anonay, France) equipped with a rotor of 45 disks engraved with 32 partition cells was used. The solvents were pumped through a preparative ECP2000 pump (Ecom, Prague, Czech Republic) and the fractions were collected by a C6–60 collector (Büchi, Flawil, Switzerland). NMR spectra were acquired on a Bruker AVANCE III 600 MHz spectrometer, equipped with a z-gradient inverse detection 5 mm probe (proton frequency of 600.113 MHz, $B_0 = 14.1$ T) or on a Bruker Avance NEO 400 MHz spectrometer in deuterated chloroform-*d* ($CDCl_3$) and methanol-*d*₄ (MeOD) (Merck SA, Athens, Greece). Semi-preparative HPLC was performed on a ECOM TOY18DAD H detector using a FORTIS C-18 (5 μ m, 250 \times 10 mm) semi-preparative column. Flash chromatography was performed on silica gel 60 A (0.040–0.060 mm) (Merck SA, Athens, Greece). Merck Silica gel F₂₅₄ plates (Merck SA, Athens, Greece) were used for thin layer chromatography (TLC). Detection of the spots on TLC was conducted under

UV light or by spraying with vanillin–sulfuric acid and heating. High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (HRMS) spectra were recorded on a time of flight (triple-TOF 5600+, AB SCIEX) system equipped with a Duo-Spray ion source, operated in the positive electrospray ionization (ESI) mode. The elucidation of all structures and configurations was carried out by 1D and 2D NMR spectroscopic analysis, HRMS experiments and bibliography data.

2.2. Plant material

The whole plant of *Artemisia umbelliformis* subsp. *eriantha* was collected during the flowering stage in August 2020 on Mount Smolikas, at an ophiolite substrate, and an altitude of 2,550–2,630 m above sea level (a.s.l.). Plant collection and identification was carried out by Dr. E. Kalpoutzakis. Voucher specimen (SM023) is kept at the Herbarium of the Division of Pharmacognosy and Natural Product Chemistry (Department of Pharmacy, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Athens, Greece). Detailed photographs of the plant material from Mount Smolikas were also recorded (Fig. 1).

2.3. Extraction and CPC fractionation for HetCA

Initially, 300 g of dried and powdered plant material were extracted by ultrasonication with 2.5 L of ethyl acetate (EtOAc) (2 cycles of 40 min each, at 30 °C). The obtained extract was filtered and evaporated to dryness under vacuum to yield 7.5 g of filtered extract (2.5 % w/w). For the CPC fractionation, several biphasic systems were tested and the one showing the best dispersion of compounds between the phases was selected (Table S1). Specifically, the selected solvent system consisted of n-hex/EtOAc/MeOH/H₂O at a ratio of 6:4:5:3 (v/v/v/v). A 1000 mL column was filled with the stationary phase at a flow rate of 20 mL/min and a rotation speed of 200 rpm, in ascending mode. The mobile phase was loaded at a flow rate of 15 mL/min and a rotation speed of 620 rpm. 2.2 g of the extract diluted in 40 mL of solvent (20 mL of upper phase and 20 mL of lower phase) were injected. The CPC fractionation was performed in ascending mode, at a flow rate of 15 mL/min and rotational speed of 620 rpm and, resulting in the collection of 50 elution fractions of 20 mL. Extrusion of the column content was achieved by pumping the upper phase in ascending mode at a flow rate 20 mL/min and rotational speed of 620 rpm, leading to the collection of 60 extrusion fractions of 20 mL. All fractions were monitored by TLC analysis, and they were

pooled to 48 final fractions in the attempt to create a concentration variation of the different components in subsequent fractions as seen in Fig. S1.

2.4. NMR sample preparation for HetCA analysis

For the preparation of the samples, prior to NMR analysis, 5 mg of each fraction were diluted in 600 µL of MeOD +0.02 % v/v HMDSO. NMR spectra for HetCA were acquired at 600 MHz, using a pulse sequence derived from the two-dimensional NOESY experiment for detection and water suppression and 64 K points in the time domain. The experiment temperature was set at 298 K. Experiments were conducted with the IconNMR suite by Bruker and with the help of a 60-place sample changer (B-ACS-60). All the acquired spectra were automatically phase- and baseline corrected. Chemical shifts were reported with respect to HMDSO at 0 ppm.

2.5. Data processing and statistical analysis

HetCA and STOCSY analysis were carried out in certain fraction groups to avoid overlapping of compounds derived from different fractions. Raw data from NMR were imported into the Matlab suite (version R2022b) and highly resolved buckets were created. Specifically, the NMR spectra (spectral width from –0.3 to 10.5 ppm) were segmented into 21,600 equal-sized bins with a bin size of 0.0005 ppm. The covariance and correlation between the intensities of the NMR resonances and the obtained activity were calculated using *in-house* routines known as HetCA. The resulting covariance values were presented as an NMR pseudospectrum. STOCSY analysis was performed using a driver peak from the generated HetCA pseudospectra. In more detail, using the same set of NMR buckets and an *in-house* Matlab routine, the covariance between a driver peak and other NMR resonances was calculated and the output was a pseudospectrum where correlated peaks presented the same fluctuation in intensity across the different spectra.

2.6. Assessing drug efficacy against *Leishmania infantum* promastigotes

Leishmania infantum promastigotes (strain GH8, MHOM/GR/2001/GH8), were cultured in tissue flasks at 26 °C in complete RPMI- 1640 medium supplemented with 2 mM L-glutamine, 10 mM HEPES, 24 mM NaHCO₃, 100 U/mL penicillin, 100 µg/mL streptomycin and 10 % (v/v)

Fig. 1. *Artemisia umbelliformis* subsp. *eriantha* from mount Smolikas.

heat-inactivated foetal bovine serum. The anti-leishmanial activity of the *Artemisia umbelliformis* subsp. *eriantha* fractions were determined with the use of resazurin (7-Hydroxy-3H-phenoxazin-3-one 10-oxide sodium salt) reduction assay. More specifically, 2.5×10^6 late-logarithmic-phase *L. infantum* promastigotes were seeded into 96-well plates and the fractions were tested in triplicates at the standard concentration of 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (in total volume 200 μL). Plates were incubated at 26 °C for 72 h and upon this period, 20 μL of resazurin (20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) were added and plates were further incubated for 24 h. Then, the optical density was determined at 570 nm with a reference wavelength at 630 nm. The absorbance in the absence of any drug was set as the 100 % positive control. The anti-promastigote activity of pure compounds was tested at the standard concentration of 10 μM .

Compounds, fractions and extracts were dialyzed in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and in all instances the volume of DMSO and dialyzed extracts (drug) was below 0.5 (v/v) %. The half maximal effective concentration (EC_{50}) against *L. infantum* promastigotes was calculated using a nonlinear regression curve fit with increasing concentrations of each compound. In addition, the cytotoxicity of each compound was tested on THP-1 cells in a 96-well format. Briefly, 4×10^4 suspension cells per well, were treated with 100 nM phorbol myristate acetate (PMA) in fully supplemented RPMI-1640 medium. Cells were left to differentiate to macrophages for 48 h at 37 °C, 5 % CO_2 . Various increasing compound concentrations were added for 72 h. Then the CC_{50} value (50 % cytotoxic concentration) was determined with a resazurin assay.

Finally, the anti-amastigote killing activity was also assessed with the resazurin cell viability assay. 4×10^4 suspension THP-1 cells, were seeded in a well in 96 well plates, in fully complemented RPMI-1640 medium. THP-1 cells were then differentiated to macrophages by the addition of 100 nM PMA for 48 h at 37 °C, 5 % CO_2 . Cells were infected with stationary phase promastigotes, at a ratio of 10 parasites per macrophage for 6 h at 37 °C, 5 % CO_2 . Free parasites were washed with PBS thrice and fresh medium supplemented with 20 nM PMA, was added. Compound 1 was added in selected concentrations. After 72 h, the supernatant was removed, cell membranes were disrupted with 100 μL 0.01 % (w/v) SDS in PBS per well, and complete Schneider's insect medium supplemented with 20 % (v/v) FBS (100 $\mu\text{L}/\text{well}$) was added. Plates were further incubated at 26 °C for 72 h in order to achieve the transformation of viable amastigotes into promastigotes. The resazurin solution (60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) was added to each well and the plates were further incubated for 24 h at 26 °C. The results described are representative of at least three independent experiments.

2.7. Isolation

^1H NMR of the consequent fractions was used as a driver for targeted isolation of the compounds. Fractions 21–30 were combined (140 mg) and subjected to column chromatography on silica gel with c-hex/EtOAc gradient elution (from 100:0 to 0:100) producing five subfractions (A–E), to yield 5-deoxy-5-hydroperoxytelekin 1 (12.5 mg) and telekin 2 (12.9 mg). The aldehyde isoinunal 3 (3.5 mg, $t_{\text{R}} = 7.3$ min) was purified from subfraction D (10.0 mg) by semi-preparative HPLC separation using gradient solvent system (MeOH/ H_2O 60:40 to 100:0) and a flow of 3.5 mL/min. Preparative TLC of combined fractions 32 and 33 (15.0 mg) on silica gel glass plate with c-hex/EtOAc 50:50 yielded 2.3 mg of 5-deoxy-5-hydroperoxy-5-epitelekin 4 ($\text{Rf} = 0.72$). Preparative TLC of

combined fractions 35 and 36 (15.0 mg) on silica gel glass plate developed 3 times with c-hex/EtOAc 60:40 yielded 4.0 mg of bonanzin 5 ($\text{Rf} = 0.59$) and 6.0 mg of 4(15)- β -epoxyisotelekin ($\text{Rf} = 0.65$). Fractions 5–14 were combined (111 mg) and chromatographed onto a silica gel column using a c-hex/EtOAc gradient solvent system (from 100:0 to 0:100) producing eleven subfractions (F–P) to yield (Z)-B-ring-homotonghaosu 8 (8.7 mg), and (E)- tonghaosu 9 (10.0 mg). Fraction I (16 mg) was purified by preparative TLC on silica gel glass plate with mobile phase c-hex/EtOAc 70:30, to afford alloalantolactone 7 (1.9 mg) at $\text{Rf} = 0.74$.

2.8. Compound characterization

5-deoxy-5-hydroperoxytelekin (1): White amorphous solid; ^1H and ^{13}C NMR data, see Table S2; HRMS m/z 231.1380 [$\text{M}-\text{H}_2\text{O}_2+\text{H}$] $^+$ (calcd for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$, 231.1380).

Telekin (2): White crystal solid; ^1H and ^{13}C NMR data, see Table S3; HRMS m/z 231.1379 [$\text{M}-\text{H}_2\text{O}+\text{H}$] $^+$ (calcd for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$, 231.1380).

Isoinunal (3): Colorless oil; ^1H and ^{13}C NMR data, see Table S4; HRMS m/z 229.1230 [$\text{M}-\text{H}_2\text{O}+\text{H}$] $^+$ (calcd for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$, 229.1233).

5-deoxy-5-hydroperoxy-5-epitelekin (4): White amorphous solid; ^1H and ^{13}C NMR data, see Table S5; HRMS m/z 231.1372 [$\text{M}-\text{H}_2\text{O}_2+\text{H}$] $^+$ (calcd for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$, 231.1380).

Bonanzin (5): Yellow crystals; ^1H and ^{13}C NMR data, see Table S6; HRMS m/z 375.1093 [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ (calcd for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_8$, 375.1074).

4(15)- β -epoxyisotelekin (6): White crystal solid; ^1H and ^{13}C NMR data, see Table S7; HRMS m/z 247.1327 [$\text{M}-\text{H}_2\text{O}+\text{H}$] $^+$ (calcd for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$, 247.1340).

Alloalantolactone (7): Colorless oil; ^1H and ^{13}C NMR data, see Table S8; HRMS m/z [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ 233.1538 (calcd for, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$, 233.1536).

(Z)-B-ring-homo-tonghaosu (8): Yellowish oil; ^1H and ^{13}C NMR data, see Table S9; HRESIMS m/z 215.1064 [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ (calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2$, 215.1067)

(E)-Tonghaosu (9): Brownish oil; ^1H and ^{13}C NMR data, see Table S10; HRMS m/z 201.0916 [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ (calcd for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2$, 201.0910)

3. Results and discussion

In the present study, the *Artemisia umbelliformis* subsp. *eriantha* ethyl acetate extract was selected after screening various Greek *Artemisia* species against *Leishmania infantum* promastigotes, exhibiting an EC_{50} of 12.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (Fig. S54). The extract of *Artemisia umbelliformis* subsp. *eriantha* was subjected to CPC fractionation using a biphasic solvent system composed of n-hex/EtOAc/MeOH/ H_2O . It is important to note that the choice of the solvent system, as well as the final solvent ratio plays a critical role in the success of the approach. In principle, the system is determined based on the distribution of the compounds between the two phases [31]. Given the intended use of HetCA in this study, fractionation was designed such that each constituent is distributed across a series of consecutive fractions, creating concentration variations (Fig. S1, S2). This concentration variance represents a crucial step in the process, as it enables the correlation of the NMR signal intensities, with the bioactivity results, both of which depend on the concentration of the different compounds. Also, the number of fractions is important to enabling both the adequate compounds distribution as

Fig. 2. Inhibition (%) of *L. infantum* promastigotes growth in parasites treated with fractions F1–F48 of *Artemisia umbelliformis* subsp. *eriantha* at 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and set of spectra analyzed.

well as NMR analysis and bioactivity assessment. From the 48 final fractions, aliquots of 5 mg and 1 mg were prepared for ^1H NMR analysis and bioactivity assays, respectively. The fractions were tested against *L. infantum* GH8 promastigotes at a fixed concentration of 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, yielding growth inhibition percentages ranging from 0 to 100 % (Fig. 2). The bioactivity data were then correlated with the spectral data of the fractions using HetCA. The covariance factors between NMR signal intensities and corresponding bioactivity were visualized in the form of a pseudospectrum, in which peaks were colour-coded according to the correlation power. Red regions represented “hot” NMR features positively correlated with the bioactivity, whereas blue ones corresponded to “cold” negatively correlated signals. Hot peaks indicated by HetCA were used as “driver” peaks for Statistical Total Correlation Spectroscopy (STOCSY). STOCSY functions similarly to HetCA in respect to visual outcome via pseudospectra tool indicative of compound structure. The combined use of HetCA for detection of possibly active compounds and STOCSY as a powerful dereplication tool leads synergistically to rational selection and targeted isolation of bioactives. Both HetCA and STOCSY were carried out on selected fraction groups to minimize spectral overlapping from different compounds. Following this approach, four groups of spectra were selected according to the observed bioactivity maxima namely F6–11, F23–27, F27–31, F31–34 (Fig. 2). The most prominent anti-leishmanial activity was observed for fraction series F23 to F34, with three distinct local maxima.

The first set of spectra examined was F23–27 where F25 and F26 displayed the strongest inhibition. HetCA revealed a set of NMR peaks positively correlated with bioactivity, attributed to two structurally similar compounds. Positively correlated signals included doublets at δ 6.02, 6.01, 5.64 and 5.60, singlets at δ 4.95, 4.77, 4.65 and 4.62, multiplets at δ 4.56–4.51 and 3.33–3.22, methyl singlets at δ 0.93 and 0.87 and a series of multiplets between δ 2.30–1.40. STOCSY analysis driven by targeting a characteristic intense peak at δ 6.02, correlated this signal with the peaks at δ 5.64, 4.95, 4.65, 4.54, 3.31, 0.93 and the multiplets between δ 2.30–1.40 range, suggesting a single compound. Based on spectral data and literature on *A. umbelliformis* secondary metabolites, this compound was tentatively identified as the eudesmanolide 5-deoxy-5-hydroperoxytelekin 1 [32,33] (Fig. 3). Similarly, STOCSY analysis centered on δ 6.01, correlated the peaks at δ 5.60, 4.77, 4.62, 4.52, 3.28 and 0.87, leading to the tentative identification of the respective alcohol telekin 2 [34,35]. Further, in order to validate this identification, both compounds were subsequently isolated, purified and fully characterized by 1D and 2D NMR spectroscopy (Table S2, S3, Fig. S7–S13, Fig. S14–S20). As shown in Fig. 3 the 1D spectrum of 1 is in perfect agreement with the STOCSY plots and the same holds for compound 2 (Fig. S3).

In the next set of spectra F27–31, additional correlated peaks were observed, including those previously identified in F23–27 (compounds 1 and 2). Notably, new signals included an aldehydic proton peak at δ 10.10 and two exomethylene protons at δ 6.17 (d, $J = 2.5$ Hz) and 5.78 (d, $J = 2.2$ Hz). (Fig. 4). Taking as driver peak the doublet at δ 6.17, STOCSY indicated that these peaks originated from a single molecule (Fig. S4) which presented structural similarities with compounds 1 and 2 exhibiting also a very similar covariance with activity. Following isolation and NMR characterization, this compound was identified as isoinal 3 (Table S4, Fig. S21–S25), a plant-growth-regulating eudesmanolide from *Inula racemosa* [36] and *Artemisia verlotorum* [37], but not yet reported as a constituent of *A. umbelliformis*.

HetCA of F31–34 again indicated peaks attributed to the previously identified compounds 1 and 2 both present in F23–27 and F27–31. Additional signals comprised the doublets at δ 6.05 ($J = 1.5$ Hz) and 5.70 ($J = 1.3$ Hz), the singlets at δ 5.12 and 5.07, a multiplet at δ 4.53 (Fig. 5). STOCSY analysis of reference peak at δ 6.05 correlated this peak with peaks at δ 5.12, 5.07, 4.53, 2.54, 2.44, 2.04, 0.98 (Fig. S5). This compound was tentatively identified as 5-deoxy-5-hydroperoxy-5-epitelekin 4, based on literature data [32,34]. Isolation and NMR experiments verified the characterization of compound 4 (Table S5, Fig. S26–S29).

The final fraction set analyzed was F6–11, where a slightly lower parasite growth inhibition was observed. The pseudospectrum-HetCA plot for F6–11 is shown in Fig. 6. Positively correlated signals between δ 5.5 and 6.2 were observed, indicating three potentially active compounds bearing exomethylenes, while the maximum activity of F9 coincided with the maximum intensity of these peaks as shown in the stack plot presentation of NMR spectra in Fig. 7. More precisely, the peaks at δ 6.02 and 5.64 corresponded to the exomethylene at position 13 of 5-deoxy-5-hydroperoxytelekin 1, while those at δ 6.05 and 5.70 to the exomethylene at position 13 of 5-deoxy-5-hydroperoxy-5-epitelekin 4 as seen previously. The doublets at δ 6.09 ($J = 2.3$ Hz) and 5.65 ($J = 2.3$ Hz) suggested a closely related metabolite. STOCSY analysis driven by targeting the characteristic intense peak at δ 5.65, correlated this signal with peaks at δ 6.09, 4.48, 2.83, 1.62, 1.03 (Fig. S6). Based on these spectral signals and literature reports, this compound was tentatively identified as alloalantolactone 7 [38] (Table S8, Fig. S39–43), a precursor metabolite of the isomeric hydroperoxyeudesmanolides 1 and 2 reported in *A. umbelliformis* [27]. Compound 7 has been also isolated from *Inula helenium*, exhibiting significant anti-inflammatory activity [39].

In addition, interesting scaffolds not previously described in the literature for *A. umbelliformis* were revealed using mainly STOCSY. Although negatively correlated with bioactivity, the detected spin-

Fig. 3. A. HetCA plot of F23–27 spectra set; deep red colored peaks indicate higher correlation with activity. B. STOCSY with driver peak at δ 6.02, showing the signals correlated and attributed to the same compound, C. ^1H NMR spectrum of pure compound **1** in MeOD in perfect agreement with the HetCA and STOCSY plot. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. HetCA plot of Fr27–31 spectra set. Correlated peaks at δ 10.10, 6.17, and 5.78 derive from compound **3** shown in the inset.

Fig. 5. HetCA plot of F31–34 spectra set. **A.** Red (positively correlated) peaks at δ 6.05 and 5.70 correspond to the H-13 exomethylene of compound **4**, blue (negatively correlated) peak at δ 5.97 corresponds to the H-13 of compound **6**. **B.** Red (positively correlated) peaks of exomethylenes of position 15 of compounds **1**, **2** and **4** at δ 4.6–5.2. **C.** Blue (negatively correlated) peaks of the ABX system of compound **5**. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 6. HetCA plot of F6–11 spectra set. A. Red-labeled (positively correlated) peaks at δ 6.10–5.60 belong to the exomethylene at position 13 of compounds 1, 4 and 7. B. Red (positively correlated) peaks at δ 5.20–4.60 belong to the exomethylene at position 15 of compounds 1 and 4. Red (positively correlated) multiplet of H-8 of compounds 1 and 4 at δ 4.54 and of compound 7 at δ 4.48. C. Blue-labeled (negatively correlated) doublet at δ 6.56 corresponds to the H-8 of compound 8. D. Blue (negatively correlated) peaks at δ 3.90–3.70 correspond to H-14 of compounds 8 and 9. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 7. Stack plot of the ^1H NMR region δ 3.5–7.0 of *Artemisia umbelliformis* subsp. *Eriantha* F6–11 along with the *L. infantum* growth inhibition profile displayed on the left side of the figure. Maximum antileishmanial activity coincides with maximum intensity of the H-15 exomethylene peaks attributed to compounds 1, 4 and 7 as indicated by the dashed red ellipse. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. Chemical structures of compounds 1–9; 5-deoxy-5-hydroperoxytelekin (1), telekin (2), isoinunal (3), 5-deoxy-5-hydroperoxy-5-epitelekin (4), bonanzin (5), 4(15)- β -epoxyisotelekin (6), alloalantolactone (7), (*Z*)-B-ring-homo-tonghaosu (8), (*E*)-tonghaosu (9).

Table 1

% of *L. infantum* promastigotes growth inhibition exposed to compounds 1–9 at 10 μ M.

Compound	Name	% inhibition
1	5-deoxy-5-hydroperoxytelekin	94 \pm 3
2	Telekin	67 \pm 4
3	Isoinunal	n.d.*
4	5-deoxy-5-hydroperoxy-5-epitelekin	n.d.*
5	Bonanzin	35 \pm 3
6	4(15)- β -epoxyisotelekin	24 \pm 5
7	Alloalantolactone	27 \pm 5
8	(<i>Z</i>)-B-ring-homo-tonghaosu	11 \pm 3
9	(<i>E</i>)-tonghaosu	n.d.*
Standard drug 1	Amphotericin B (0.07 μ M)	86 \pm 4
Standard drug 2	Miltefosine (6.1 μ M)	89 \pm 2

* inhibition not detected.

systems could possibly indicate not previously reported compounds highlighting the value of STOCSY as a useful dereplication tool. More specifically, in F31–34 such signals comprised of a doublet of doublets at δ 7.69 ($J = 8.6, 2.1$ Hz), two doublets at δ 7.65 ($J = 2.1$ Hz) and 7.06 ($J = 8.6$ Hz) indicating an ABX aromatic system as well as two singlets at δ 5.97 and 5.55, which present similarity with the exomethylene of the eudesmanolides described above (Fig. 5). After isolation these compounds were identified as bonanzin 5 [40] (Table S6, Fig. S30-S33) and 4(15)- β -epoxyisotelekin 6 [35,41] (Table S7, Fig. S34-S38) and are reported for the first time in *A. umbelliformis*. Compound 5 has been reported in various *Artemisia* species such as *Artemisia annua* [42] and *Artemisia argyi* [43], while compound 6 has been only isolated from *Artemisia verlotorum* [37] and examined for anti-inflammatory activity. In F6–11, blue (negatively correlated) signals comprised of a doublet ($J = 5.8$ Hz) at δ 6.56, a singlet at δ 4.86 and two multiplets between δ 3.7 and 3.9 (Fig. 6). After isolation, the anti-correlated components were identified as the polyacetylenes (*Z*)-B-ring-homo-tonghaosu 8 [44] (Table S9, Fig. S44-S48) and (*E*)-tonghaosu 9 [45] (Table S10, Fig. S49-S53), also reported for the first time in *A. umbelliformis*. Compound 8 has

been purified from *Artemisia pallens* and assessed for antibacterial activity [44], whereas compound 9 has been isolated from *Artemisia integrifolia*, exhibiting antihyperlipidemic effects [46].

Determining the promising fractions based either on HetCA or STOCSY and aiming at structure confirmation and the validation of the approach, targeted isolation took place. In total, 9 compounds were purified and structurally identified using 1 and 2D NMR spectra and HRMS/MS (Fig. 8), allowing a further bioactivity step using the same assay for verification purposes.

Specifically, pure compounds 1–9 were tested against *L. infantum* promastigotes at a concentration of 10 μ M (Table 1), as a cutoff value to select compounds for further EC₅₀ determination. Interestingly 5-deoxy-5-hydroperoxytelekin 1 and telekin 2 were the most active ones, producing an inhibition of 94 and 67 % respectively, while compounds 3, 4, 8 and 9 showed no activity and compounds 5, 6 and 7 showed only moderate growth inhibition.

The most prominent compounds, compounds 1 and 2, were further evaluated for the determination of the EC₅₀ against *L. infantum* promastigotes. The EC₅₀ values were calculated at 4.5 μ M and 5.1 μ M; respectively, while remaining non-toxic (Fig. S55, S56). CC₅₀ values against THP-1 macrophages were determined at 29.7 μ M and 15.0 μ M. 5-deoxy-5-hydroperoxytelekin 1 exhibited a selectivity index (SI) against *L. infantum* promastigotes relative to THP-1 human cells, of 6.6 whereas telekin 2 exhibited a SI of 2.9 (Table 2). Intracellular amastigote screening also confirmed the antileishmanial activity of compound 1, suggestive of a half maximal effective concentration \leq 5 μ M (data not shown). These results indicate that 5-deoxy-5-hydroperoxytelekin 1 is

Table 2

Antileishmanial activity, cytotoxicity against THP-1 cells and promastigotes over THP-1 cells SI.

Compound	EC ₅₀ against <i>L. infantum</i> promastigotes	CC ₅₀ against THP-1 cells	SI
1	4.5 \pm 1.6 μ M	29.7 \pm 6.4 μ M	6.6
2	5.1 \pm 0.48 μ M	15 \pm 3.2 μ M	2.9

the most promising anti-leishmanial compound, yielding the best selectivity index.

HetCA has been proposed as a method to accelerate the discovery of bioactive compounds from plant extracts. In this study we tried to validate the HetCA protocols, as well as Statistical Spectroscopy, applying the approach in the analysis of *A. umbelliformis*. Combination of HetCA and STOCSY could indicate the most active compounds as seen in this study for compounds 1 and 2. In fractions F23 to F34, active compounds 1 and 2 were present in different proportions, justifying the strong bioactivity of F23–27, F27–31 and F31–34. Positive correlation to bioactivity of compound 3 from F27–31, compound 4 from F31–34 and compound 7 from F6–11 was attributed to the coelution and similar fluctuation of these compounds with the most potent compounds 1 and 2. Co-elution and co-fluctuation of components which present close structural similarity is often expected in natural products. On the other hand, absence of correlation with bioactivity, indicated by blue-labeled (negatively correlated) peaks of compounds 5, 6, 8 and 9, was verified as none of these compounds exhibited any intense activity. Compounds 1, 2, 4 and 7 were previously isolated from *A. umbelliformis* [27], while compounds 3, 5, 6, 8 and 9 are reported for the first time in the plant studied. Some of the above compounds were not fully characterized, so here we provide a more clarified characterization.

To gain better insight into the Structure Activity Relationships (SAR) revealed by the activity assays, simple energy minimization calculations were performed to obtain the optimised geometries of the six isolated eudesmanes as shown in Fig. S57. Regarding biological activity, although these compounds share the same basic skeleton, only compounds 1 and 2 exhibited activity. Compounds 3 and 4 were found to be inactive, while compounds 6 and 7 showed moderate inhibition at a concentration of 10 μM (Table 1). The bioactivity of compounds 1 and 2 appears to depend on a specific absolute configuration, the presence of an exomethylene group at position 4, and the substituent at position 5. A comparison of compounds 1 and 4 indicates that the *cis* configuration of the fused six-membered rings is detrimental to parasite growth inhibition. The *cis* configuration implies a bend structure with the hydroperoxyl substituent oriented differently compared to the *trans* configuration in compound 1. The difference in activity of compounds 2 and 6 underscores the importance of the exomethylene group at position 4, as the epoxypropyl group of compound 6 results in only moderate inhibition. The low to moderate activity of compounds 3 and 7 further demonstrates the critical role of the exomethylene group at position 4.

Active compounds 1 and 2 exhibit identical configurations, with the sole distinction being the substituent at position 5. It seems that the presence of hydroperoxyl group in place of hydroxyl group at position 5 not only enhances the compound's efficacy against the parasite but also reduces its toxicity to THP-1 macrophages. Therefore, it appears that the hydroperoxyl group plays a pivotal role in determining parasite selectivity. To date, the pharmacological target or specific enzyme inhibition of compounds 1 and 2 remains unidentified. Compound 2 has been reported to induce apoptosis in hepatocellular carcinoma cells through a mitochondria-mediated pathway [47], whereas no bioactivity has been documented for compound 1. Compound 1 demonstrates a favorable selectivity index (SI) and holds promise as a lead compound for the development of novel antileishmanial agents with improved properties, thereby opening avenues for further research in this field.

4. Conclusions

Artemisia umbelliformis subsp. *eriantha* (Asteraceae) was investigated for its antileishmanial potential, representing the first comprehensive evaluation of this subspecies in the context of Leishmania infection.

A CPC-based fractionation strategy was employed alongside the HetCA, enabling the correlation of compound concentration patterns with bioactivity data. Additionally, STOCSY was used as a powerful dereplication tool to identify known constituents within the complex extract matrix. This integrated workflow led to the targeted isolation of

six sesquiterpene lactones, two polyacetylenes, and one flavonoid. Notably, HetCA revealed a sesquiterpene lactone exhibiting potent activity, with an EC_{50} of 4.5 μM against *Leishmania infantum* promastigotes and a good SI over mammalian cells (6.6). This study not only contributes valuable insights into the potential of *A. umbelliformis* subsp. *eriantha* as a source of novel bioactive compounds but also shows the first application of HetCA for analyzing bioactivity data in whole-organism systems such as Leishmania parasites.

The successful validation of HetCA through the isolation of active constituents highlights its utility in streamlining the natural product discovery process, offering a more targeted and efficient approach to identifying bioactive compounds prior to labor-intensive purification steps.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Olga Karoutzou: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Stavros Beteinakis:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Formal analysis. **Olga Koutsoni:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation. **Eleftherios Kalpoutzakis:** Investigation. **Despina Smirlis:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation. **Maria Halabalaki:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Leandros Alexios Skaltsounis:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Emmanuel Mikros:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Olga Karoutzou reports financial support was provided by Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation. Alexios-Leandros Skaltsounis reports financial support was provided by European Union. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioorg.2025.108632>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Glossary

HetCA: Heterocovariance Approach
STOCYSY: Statistical Total Correlation Spectroscopy
CPC: Centrifugal Partition Chromatography